

Thin Layer Chromatography of Primary Aromatic Amines on Zirconium Molybdophosphate – Silica Gel G

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Thin layer chromatography of sixteen primary aromatic amine hydrochlorides has been investigated on the zirconium molybdophosphate – silica gel G with respect to the influences of zirconium molybdophosphate (ZMP) concentration in the layer and concentrations of sodium nitrate and hydrochloric acid in the eluent. Many interesting separations (qualitative and quantitative) of amine hydrochlorides from their synthetic mixtures have been observed.

Silica gel impregnated with different salts has been used earlier in the thin layer chromatographic studies of aromatic amines¹. Impregnation of thin layer plates with other substances has been tried to improve separation of amines². Synthetic inorganic ion exchangers have great promise in column, paper and thin layer chromatographic separations of amines³.

The present investigation is an attempt to explore the possibility of using zirconium molybdophosphate (ZMP) mixed with silica gel G for chromatographic studies of primary aromatic amines. The effect of ZMP concentration in modifying the separation ability of silica gel G has been studied.

Results and Discussion

The inorganic exchanger (ZMP) enhances binding capacity with the glass plates in addition to the improvement in selectivity for amine hydrochlorides. The ion exchange behavior of ZMP and adsorption behavior of silica gel G jointly influences the separation mechanism. Increase in concentration of ZMP in the thin layer resulted a decrease in R_f values but the sequence of R_f values remained unaltered (Table 1). For comparison, amine hydrochlorides were also chromatographed on plain silica gel G under similar experimental conditions. Most of the amines moved faster with almost same R_f values among isomers on plain silica gel G.

The R_f values with changing salt concentration in the eluent are recorded in Table 1. The protonated amines moved faster (higher R_f values) with the increased salt concentration. It seems due to elution of protonated amines by sodium ions (counter ions). R_f values also increase with the decreased pH of the eluent (Table 1). This 'desorption' of amine ions seems to be the determining factor in the chromatographic behavior of most amines, at least in presence of higher salt and acid concentrations in the eluent. Addition of ZMP to silica gel G promotes a differential migration of amine hydrochlorides perhaps due to combined ef-

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF PRIMARY AROMATIC AMINE HYDROCHLORIDES ON THIN LAYERS OF SILICA GEL G (SG)-ZIRCONIUM MOLYBDOPHOS-PHATE (ZMP) WITH VARYING ZMP : SG RATIO, CONC. OF SODIUM NITRATE AND pH VALUES

Amine-HCl	ZMP : SG ratio*		[NaNO ₃]**M		pH**	
	2 : 4	4 : 4	0.1	2.0	0.0	6.0
Aniline	0.40	0.38	0.19	0.52	0.43	0.12
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	0.60	0.57	0.32	0.70	0.35	0.10
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	0.45	0.40	0.30	0.58	0.30	0.10
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	0.24	0.20	0.19	0.32	0.37	0.12
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	0.38	0.33	0.14	0.46	0.38	0.09
<i>m</i> -Anisidine	0.37	0.32	0.16	0.48	0.42	0.10
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	0.35	0.32	0.16	0.48	0.46	0.11
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	0.49	0.46	0.33	0.56	0.58	0.16
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	0.46	0.44	0.28	0.54	0.42	0.10
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	0.44	0.38	0.26	0.52	0.40	0.12
α -Naphthylamine	0.44	0.39	0.19	0.56	0.38	0.11
β -Naphthylamine	0.20	0.20	0.10	0.30	0.24	0.04
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	0.56	0.50	0.35	0.66	0.45	0.22
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline	0.52	0.45	0.34	0.60	0.40	0.18
<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	0.46	0.40	0.32	0.56	0.49	0.12
2,5-Dimethoxyaniline	0.48	0.46	0.39	0.54	0.39	0.08

*Eluent : 1 M NaNO₃. **ZMP : SG ratio = 2 : 4.

fect of the ion exchange behavior of ZMP and the adsorption behavior of silica gel G. The separations which on the basis of R_f values were likely to be effective were tried. The qualitative and quantitative separations have been achieved experimentally and the results within -0.80 to +1.40% actual values.

Experimental

All reagents were of AnalaR grade amine hydrochlorides were prepared by passing dry HCl gas into amine solutions in ether. The amine hydrochlorides were formed in solid or liquid form immiscible with ether. 1% (w/v) solutions of amine hydrochlorides were prepared in distilled water.

Zirconium molybdophosphate⁴ was synthesized by mixing aqueous solution of 12-molybdophosphoric acid (36.12 g/400 ml) and zirconium oxychloride (32.23 g/500 ml). Zirconium molybdophosphate thus precipitated was digested in a steam-bath for 30 min, allowed to stand for 24 h, filtered, washed with demineralized water, dried at $90 \pm 2^\circ$ and powdered (200–300 mesh).

Thin layers of 0.2 mm thickness were prepared either of the pure silica gel G (containing *ca* 13% calcium sulfate) or the mixtures of zirconium molybdophosphate and silica gel G on glass plates (20 × 3.0 cm) and dried first at room temperature (30°) and then at 100° for 1 h.

The test solutions were spotted on the tlc plates. The developers were allowed to ascend a 11 cm on the plates at 30°. After drying at room temperature the spots were detected by spraying *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-aminobenzaldehyde (1%, w/v) in ethanol-HCl (95 : 5). For quantitative separations, the corresponding portions of the spots were scratched out, the amines extracted with small portions of iron(III) nitrate solution (1%, w/v), total 5 ml being used for complete elution and analyzed spectrophotometrically⁵ using a

Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 instrument.

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